

A Study on Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Ni (II)

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Three series of six co-ordinated complexes of Nickel(II) bis Pyridine-dicarboxylate with different heterocyclic bases like Py., α -pic., β -pic., γ -pic., Lutidine, Collidine etc., have been prepared in pure crystalline form. The Pyridine dicarboxylic acids so far studied included Lutidinic acid, (Pyridine 2 : 6 dicarboxylic acid, also known as dipicolinic acid), Quinolinic acid (Pyridine 2 : 3 dicarboxylic acid) and chelidamic acid (4-hydroxypyridine 2 : 6 dicarboxylic acid).

Lutidinic acid and Quinolinic acid behaved in an exactly similar manner. The mother compounds of both the series were of the type $\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2\text{XH}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{LH}_2 =$ Pyridine dicarboxylic acid and was prepared by mixing fairly concentrated solutions of the ligand and NiSO_4 or NiCl_2 and keeping overnight in a refrigerator, when well-defined shining crystals separated. The adducts with heterocyclic bases were prepared by adding an excess of the appropriate heterocyclic base to the mother compound, evaporating on water bath, cooling and washing with acetone. These adducts were of the type $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2\text{X}_2]$, where X is the heterocyclic base used.

In the case of chelidamic acid the mother compound could not be isolated and the adducts were prepared by treating the ligand with the appropriate base, dissolving in a small volume of water and mixing with a concentrated solution of NiSO_4 or NiCl_2 and then evaporating the solution on water bath until crystals appeared. It was then cooled and the crystals were filtered and washed with acetone. The general formula of these adducts was of the type $\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2(\text{X})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$.

The measured magnetic moments of all these complexes lie within the range 3.2–3.4 B.M. which is indicative of octahedral structure^{1,2}.

Electronic absorption spectral measurement in the region 320–1000 $m\mu$ showed two absorption bands around 350 $m\mu$ and between 600–680 $m\mu$. The third band probably lies above 1000 $m\mu$ which is not uncommon³ and not without reason⁴. This also indicated octahedral structure. The low intensities of the absorption bands also points towards octahedral structure⁵.

* Previous communications were published under the name S. Ghosh.

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A few representative members of the different series of complexes along with some of their important properties are given below in Table I.

TABLE I

Complex	Colour	Percentage of Nitrogen		Percentage of Nickel		μ_{eff}
		Found	Required	Found	Required	
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Lut})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Bright green	6.14	6.05	12.81	12.68	3.27
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Lut})_2(\text{Py})_2]$	Light green	9.98	10.20	10.81	10.69	3.30
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Quin})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	Pale blue	6.77	6.56	13.66	13.75	3.20
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Quin})_2(\text{Py})_2]$	Light Pink	10.30	10.20	10.40	10.69	2.93
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Chel})_2(\text{Py})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$	Blue	8.25	8.08	11.57	11.29	3.20

Conductance measurements, I.R. Spectra, T.G.A., D.T.A. and D.T.G. studies of the above compounds are in progress and will be reported shortly.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents used for preparative work were L.R. grade while those used for estimation were A.R. variety.

Methods of analysis: Ni(II) was determined by the standard dimethyl glyoxime method after decomposing the compound with $\text{HNO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ mixture and evaporation to nearly dryness. Nitrogen was estimated by the semimicro Duma's combustion technique. Absorption spectra in ethanol in presence of heterocyclic base were recorded in Hilger-Watt Unispek Spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were done with the help of a Gouy balance using G.R. $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as the calibrant.

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Corrigendum

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The graphs shown under Figure 2 will actually belong to the Figure 3; the graphs shown under Figure 3 belong to Figure 2.